

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 65

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 65

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 65:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David. A Song.</p>	<p>Psa. 65:1 שִׁיר : 2 לְךָ יְהוָה הַמְלִיָּה תְהִלָּה אֱלֹהִים בְּצִיּוֹן וְלֹךְ יִשְׁלַם-</p>
<p>Psa. 65:1 There will be silence ¹before You, <i>and</i> praise in Zion, O God, And to You the ^avow will be performed.</p>	<p>נִדְרָ : 3 שְׁמַע תְּפִלָּה עֲדִיךָ כָּל-בָּשָׂר יִבְאוּ : 4 דְבַרְי</p>
<p>² O You who hear prayer, To You ^aall ¹men come.</p>	<p>עֹזֶנֶת גְּבִרוֹ מִנִּי פִשְׁעֵינוּ אֶתָּה תִּכְפְּרֵם : 5 אֲשֶׁר־י אֶתְבַּחַר</p>
<p>³ ^{1a}Iniquities prevail against me; As for our transgressions, You ^{2b}forgive them.</p>	<p>וּתְקַרְב־י שְׁכֵן תִּצְרִיךָ גִשְׁבָּעָה בְּטוֹב בֵּיתְךָ קָדֹשׁ הֵיכָלְךָ : 6 נֹרְאוֹת אֲבַצְדֵק תַּעֲנִנּוּ אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׁעֵנוּ מִבְּטָח כָּל-</p>
<p>⁴ How ^ablessed is the one whom You ^bchoose and bring near <i>to You</i> To dwell in Your courts. We will be ^csatisfied with the goodness of Your house, Your holy temple.</p>	<p>קִצְוֵי-אֶרֶץ וַיִּם רְחֻקִים : 7 מִכֵּין הַרִים בְּכַחוֹ נֶאֱזָר בְּגִבּוֹרָה : 8 מִשְׁבֵּית אֲשָׁוֶן יַמִּים שְׁאוֹן גְּלִיָּהֶם וְהַמּוֹן לְאֲמִים : 9 וַיִּירָאוּ אִישׁבֵי קִצּוֹת מֵאוֹתֶיךָ מוֹצְאֵי-</p>
<p>Psa. 65:5 By ^aawesome <i>deeds</i> You answer us in righteousness, O ^bGod of our salvation, You who are the trust of all the ^cends of the earth and of the farthest ^{1d}sea; ⁶ Who ^aestablishes the mountains by His strength, Being ^bgirded with might; ⁷ Who ^astills the roaring of the seas, The roaring of their waves, And the ^btumult of the peoples. ⁸ They who dwell in the ^aends <i>of the earth</i> stand in awe of Your signs; You make the ¹dawn and the sunset shout for joy.</p>	<p>בְּקָר וְעָרַב תִּרְנִין : 10 פִּקְדוֹת הָאֶרֶץ וּתְשַׁקְּקֶה רִבְת תַּעֲשֶׂרנָה פִּלְג אֱלֹהִים מִלֵּא מִים תִּכְיִן דָּגָנָם כִּי-כֵן</p>

Psa. 65:9 You visit the earth and
^acause it to overflow;
 You greatly ^benrich it;
 The ¹stream of God is full of
 water;
 You prepare their ^dgrain, for thus
 You prepare ²the earth.
¹⁰ You water its furrows abundantly,
 You ¹settle its ridges,
 You soften it ^awith showers,
 You bless its growth.
¹¹ You have crowned the year ¹with
 Your ^{2a}bounty,
 And Your ³paths ^bdrip *with* fatness.
¹² ^aThe pastures of the wilderness
 drip,
 And the ^bhills gird themselves with
 rejoicing.
¹³ The meadows are ^aclothed with
 flocks
 And the valleys are ^bcovered with
 grain;
 They ^cshout for joy, yes, they sing.

תְּכַיֵּנָהּ : ¹¹ תִּלְמִיחַ רוּחַ נִתְתַּת
 וְרוּחַיָּהּ בְּרַב־יָבִים תִּמְלֵגְנָהּ
 צְמִיחָהּ תִּבְרַךְ : ¹² עֲטִרֶתָּ שְׁנַת
 טוֹבֶתָּ וְיִמְעַגְלֶיךָ יִרְעֶפוּן
 דְּשֵׁן : ¹³ יִרְעֶפוּ נְאוֹת מְדָבָר
 וְגִיל גְּבָעוֹת תַּחֲגֹרְנָהּ : ¹⁴
 לְבָשׁוּ כְרִים אֶהְצֵאן וְעִמְקִים
 יֵעֲטְפוּ-בָרֶבֶר יִתְרוּעְעוּ אֶתְךָ-
 יִשִּׁירוּ :

References

Psalm 64:1

¹Or *concern*

^aPs 55:2

^bPs 140:1

Psalm 64:2

^aPs 56:6

^bPs 59:2

Psalm 64:3

^aPs 140:3

^bPs 58:7

Psalm 64:4

¹Lit *in*

^aPs 10:8; 11:2

^bPs 55:19

Psalm 64:5

¹Lit *make firm*

²Lit *tell of*

^aPs 140:5

^bJob 22:13; Ps 10:11

Psalm 64:6

¹Or *search out*

²Lit *complete*

³Or *inward part*

⁴Or *unsearchable*

^aPs 49:11

Psalm 64:7

¹Or *shot*

²Or *they were wounded; lit their wounds occurred*

^aPs 7:12, 13

Psalm 64:8

¹Or *they make their tongue a stumbling for themselves*

²Or *made*

^aPs 9:3

^bProv 12:13; 18:7

Ps 22:7; 44:14; Jer 18:16; 48:27; Lam 2:15

Psalm 64:9

¹Or *feared*

²Or *declared*

³Or *considered*

⁴Lit *His work*

^aPs 40:3

^bJer 51:10

Psalm 64:10

^aJob 22:19; Ps 32:11

^bPs 11:1; 25:20

Targum

Psa. 65:1 For praise, a psalm of David, a song. ² Before you praise is considered as silence, O God, whose presence is in Zion, and vows will be paid to you. ³ O receiver of prayer, unto you all the sons of flesh will come. ⁴ Words of iniquity have overcome me; you will atone for our sins. ⁵ How happy the one you will choose and bring near; he will abide in your courts. The righteous will say, "We will be satisfied in the goodness of your house, the holiness of your temple." ⁶ Accept our prayer [with] fearful deeds in righteousness, O God our redemption, the hope of all the ends of the earth, and the islands of the sea far from dry land. ⁷ Who established food for the ibexes of the mountains in the strength of his might, who is girded with a belt in might. ⁸ Who quiets the commotion of the seas and the commotion of their waves, and the hubbub of the nations. ⁹ And those who dwell at the borders were afraid at your signs; [at the] extremities of morning and evening you will set praise in their mouth. ¹⁰ You have remembered the land and watered it; you will enrich it with much produce from the vault of God which is in heaven, full of rain; you will form their grain, for thus you will consummate it. ¹¹ He has drenched those raised on its plants; he has given rest to its troops; you will bless its blossoms. ¹² You have crowned the year with the goodness of your blessings; and the paths of your way will give an odor of richness. ¹³ They will make sweet the psalms of the wilderness, and the hills will gird themselves with joy. ¹⁴ The rams will copulate with the flock, and the plains will be covered with grain; they will shout, indeed, they will rejoice.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

King David wrote this Psalm as a three-year famine had struck Israel. David prays for rain and an abundant crop. Droughts were devastating to the economy of Israel. She was an agriculturally based economy. More importantly, it meant that people were starving to death. David called upon the Sefirah Netzach, who offers spiritual victory.

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants spiritual victory, a Psalm, a Song of David.

Verse one

אֱלֹהִים בְּצִיּוֹן (ehlohim b'tzion), means “God of Zion.” It is only in Zion that

God made known to humanity that He was near and reveals his presence within the spirit of all. This is where the Neshamah of the soul can be most stirred.

Security and freedom from frustration, worry, and fear can be attained only by trusting the LORD and asking for His help.

Peace of soul is an emanation of Your mighty acts, O God in Zion, and unto you the vow is made.

Verse two

The peace of the soul is an inner activity of mind and spirit. This peace is perceived only by the LORD. Humans can create an intimate relationship with the LORD through the peace of the soul.

Of You Who hears prayer! One day all those that can feel will come unto You.

Verses three and four

Verse three contains an acknowledgment of the total evolution of human history. Individuals create complex situations brought about by their manifold errors that have grown too complex to fend off. The result is a disastrous situation.

The products of sin that are our common defection have overcome me; You will grant them atonement.

For only he whom You will choose and will bring near unto You strides forward to salvation, so that he may find a dwelling place in Your courts. We too wish to be satisfied by the goodness of Your House, which is sanctified in the Abode of your might.

Verse five

The shaping of humankind's affairs is to follow righteousness taught us through the LORD's Torah.

You answer us with awesome truths and righteousness, I God of our salvation, Who are the trust of all men, who dwell at the ends of the earth and of the distant seas.

Verse six

The LORD's creative power is manifested in all the areas of the Universe. His creative power also established the natural forces of nature.

He Who sets fast the mountains with His strength is also girded with victorious might.

Verse seven

David praises the LORD's omnipotent powers. The forces of nature on Earth demonstrate this power.

He stills the roaring of the seas, the roaring of their waves, and also the surging multitude of the peoples;

Verse eight

The Gentiles of the Earth need to acquire a reverence of the LORD. They can acquire this through the signs of the LORD's power. The LORD demonstrates His power every day.

But when the inhabitants of the most distant nations shall have learned to revere You through Your signs, You will make the goings-out of morning and evening to rejoice.

Verse nine

David elaborates upon the way to obtain the salvation which every human can achieve. They must come into the House of the LORD and follow His Laws.

You remembered the earth when You let it languish; You remain in exceedingly great abundance to it; the fountain of God is always filled with water; You will prepare their grain when You will prepare the earth thus.

Verse ten

Water its ridges now, settle down its furrows, make it soft with showers, and bless its growth.

Verse eleven

שָׁנָה (sh'nat) - means "year." The context of the word in this Psalm indicates a new period of time. It is not limited to one year.

Then you have crowned the new era (the year) of Your goodness, and the circles around you drip with abundance.

Verse twelve

The pastures of the desert drip, and the hills gird themselves with joy.

Verse thirteen

יִתְרוֹעֵנוּ (yeet'roaoo) – means “joy.” In the context of this Psalm it also means lofty emotions that are expressed in songs and rejoicing.

The meadows clothe themselves with sheep, and valleys cover themselves with grain; they fill themselves with the homage of God; indeed they sing songs beholding His greatness.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Peace of soul is an emanation of Your mighty acts, O God in Zion, and unto you the vow is made.

Of You Who hears prayer! One day all those that can feel will come unto You. The products of sin that are our common defection have overcome me; You will grant them atonement.

For only he whom You will choose and will bring near unto You strides forward to salvation, so that he may find a dwelling place in Your courts. We too wish to be satisfied by the goodness of Your House, which is sanctified in the Abode of your might.

You answer us with awesome truths and righteousness, O God of our salvation, Who are the trust of all men, who dwell at the ends of the earth and of the distant seas.

He Who sets fast the mountains with His strength is also girded with victorious might.

He stills the roaring of the seas, the roaring of their waves, and also the surging multitude of the peoples;

But when the inhabitants of the most distant nations shall have learned to revere You through Your signs, You will make the goings-out of morning and evening to rejoice.

You remembered the earth when You let it languish; You remain in exceedingly great abundance to it; the fountain of God is always filled with water; You will prepare their grain when You will prepare the earth thus.

Water its ridges now, settle down its furrows, make it soft with showers, and bless its growth.

Then you have crowned the new era (the year) of Your goodness, and the circles around you drip with abundance.

The pastures of the desert drip, and the hills gird themselves with joy.

The meadows clothe themselves with sheep, and valleys cover themselves with grain; they fill themselves with the homage of God; indeed they sing songs beholding His greatness.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

